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MEASURES TO STABILIZE THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS IN A PANDEMIC (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX OF THE TASHKENT REGION)

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Abstract

The article describes the features of the industrial development of the Tashkent region. Within one region, an industrial complex was analyzed. Some views of theorists on regional development are given. The opinions of these scientists on the factors affecting the development of industry in the region are analyzed. The economic potential and geographical location of the regions can lead to a clear division of the individual territories in industrial production. The economic and industrial potential of the Tashkent region was evaluated. It also analyzes the economic potential of the region. The role of regional sectors of the economy in the country is considered. It describes the economic potential of districts and cities, the availability of financial resources and the level of development of scientific and technological progress. It indicates the need to change the principles of state regulation of the scientific sphere for innovative development and the effective functioning of the region's industry, foreign experience is an example of organizational and economic measures supporting the innovative development of the region's industry. The composition of factors influencing the innovative development of the region's industry is also analyzed in turn.

In particular, the emphasis in innovation is on the development of the human factor, science and technology. It is known that the growth of industrial production is not due to the expansion of extensive factors, but to a well-thought-out consistent policy in a systemic market economy, attracting foreign investment, profound structural changes in the economy, modernization and renewal of production, new export-oriented industries and enterprises. organization through the development of private entrepreneurship. Particular attention is paid to the innovative development of industrial production. This makes it necessary to study the world experience in the innovative development of the region's industry. In this regard, the article also uses the results of the experience of developed countries in this area. World experience also provides examples of organizational and economic measures to support the innovative development of industry in the region. Recommendations are given on the targeted application of these measures. In conclusion, recommendations on the sustainable development of industry in the region are presented.

Keywords: Region, industry, innovation, technology park, high economic growth, innovation cluster.

I. INTRODUCTION

The pandemic is becoming a big test for the whole world. The current global crisis has a serious impact on the economies of all countries. According to the World Bank, by 2020, global GDP is expected to fall by 5.2 percent, in the United States by 6.1 percent, in Russia by 6 percent, and in the European Union by 9.1 percent. At the same time, economic growth is expected to be 1% in China and 1.5% in Uzbekistan. Therefore, the country is taking numerous measures to increase economic growth using a new approach and tools. For this, several key areas were chosen, including efforts to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of production through deep processing of raw materials and the creation of an integrated production chain for value-added products, full-fledged inter-industry cooperation in order to enhance competitiveness.

In the country, it is becoming increasingly important to "increase the share of industry in the economy, accelerate the development of high-tech industries and manufacturing industries, further modernize and diversify the industry, ensure the comprehensive and effective use of the industrial potential of each region, create new industrial enterprises and small industrial zones", "accelerate the implementation programs of modernization and increasing competitiveness in leading industries", as well as "providing industrial sectors with uninterrupted raw materials and modern infrastructure", in particular, the development of chemical, oil and gas, energy, electrical, building materials, jewelry.

The Strategy for Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021 emphasizes that "the rapid introduction of modern innovative technologies in sectors of the economy, including industry, social and other spheres with the widespread use of scientific and technological achievements, is a prerequisite for enhancing the scientific potential of research and development, and also, increasing effective mechanisms for integrating education, science and entrepreneurship for the widespread implementation of research, development and technology results, strengthening public and private investments in innovation, research, development and technology" as well as additional measures to support the population, economic and business sectors during the pandemic.

II. METHODOLOGY

The industrial complex is a branch of the economy that has a great influence on the level of development of the productive forces of society. The development of the industrial complex began in England and then spread throughout the world. If we turn to ancient history, we can see that in Arthashastra the state spent a lot of money on the development of industry [17,10]. Xenophon believed that since agriculture is the mainstay of the economy, a downturn in agriculture would also have a negative impact on industry [23,15]. According to Blaug, in order to support the industry, it was necessary to import cheap raw materials, introduce protectionist duties on imported industries, and stimulate the export of finished products. Thomas Mann believed that industry was an important sector and that industrial development would facilitate mutually beneficial foreign trade, while William Petty believed that the source of wealth was not trade and exchange, but production, and government support was important to stimulate industry. F. Kene, the founder of the school of physiocrats, believed that it is necessary to protect the industry with the help of custom tariffs, to finance the development of the industrial complex by issuing government bonds. Anne Robert Jacques Turgot viewed the industry as unproductive, calling those who worked in the industry an ineffective class. A. Smith, a representative of the classical school, opposed the idea of the physiocrats about the "inefficiency" of industry, showing the creation of wealth in industry.

Later on, the scientific research of economists in our country also contributed to the study of this problem. In particular, in the scientific works of local scientists N.K. Yuldashev [20,23], E.Kh. Makhmudov, A.A. Artikov, H. Ishbutaev, A.M. Sodikov, A.M. Kodyrov, G. Gulomova, A. Akhmediev, Alimova, M. Makhkamov, Sh. Zainutdinov, the issues of the industrial complex and its development are covered. In particular, the works emphasize the

need to create a favorable macroeconomic environment for the development of the industrial complex. In this regard, it is argued that special attention should be paid to tax, monetary, pricing and exchange rate policies. It also emphasizes the importance of the country's economic potential and geographical location in the development of industry.

Although the studies above mentioned have made a significant contribution to the development of industry and its innovative assessment in the country and its regions, it is necessary to pay particular attention to the intellectual factor, innovation and "growth points" in the development of industry in the region.

In the course of writing the article, the state of innovative development of the region was assessed, and recommendations were made based on the analysis of open statistics. In the process of studying the topic, in addition to general economic methods, special approaches to structuring data were used, such as comparison, aggregation of theoretical and practical materials, and systematic analysis.

III. DISCUSSION

The restructure of the region's economy and the transition from the extraction of raw materials to the production of high-tech products means the transition of the region's economy to the path of innovative development. In this situation, the problem of technological backwardness of regions can be solved by taking the right direction in new technological systems, increasing innovation and investment activity, increasing the influence of the state on economic dynamics and transition to a new quality of development. In the context of globalization and increasing global competition, it is difficult to achieve developed industrial production without innovative development. This indicates the specialization of regions in the division of labor among the population, as well as the need to develop high-tech industries.

In all regions, economic reforms in the industrial sector are aimed to attract local and foreign investment and launching complex types of production based on high technologies. In this regard, one of the main tasks is to attract foreign investment and advanced technologies for the implementation of industrial production based on high-tech structural requirements. In order to ensure the growth of the level and efficiency of industrial production, work is underway to expand import-substituting industries, increase export potential, develop basic industries, and increase the share of science-intensive industries. These processes are also observed in Tashkent region, which is one of the most important regions of the country [5,10].

The basis of the region's economy is metallurgy, processing and food industries, as well as the cultivation of agricultural products. Tashkent region, which is the object of the study, has great economic potential due to its geographical location and plays a significant role in the economic development of the country. One of the main advantages of the Tashkent region is the availability of production factors and natural resources, as well as additional and supporting industries. A feature of this region is its rich nature and population. The high concentration of the population in this region, the intersection of highways, as well as its historical development made it an important industrial center of the republic. The absolute dominance of the region in the production of certain types of industrial products (ferrous metals, corticosteroids, sulfuric acid, mineral waters, coal) plays a special role in the country's leading positions in the republic's industry.

The region includes 15 districts and 7 cities. The areas of this region exceed the areas of other regions of the country in terms of the level of development of their industrial potential. There are 8666 industrial enterprises in the region. These enterprises are located in cities and districts of regional importance (Almalyk, Bekabad, Akhangaron and Chirchik, Zangiotinsky and Kibray districts). The diversity of the regions' contribution to industrial production indicates the uneven distribution of industrial production in the region. Only four cities of the region produce 61.2% of the region's industrial output (Almalyk, Angren, Bekabad and Chirchik). Agricultural production in these cities is less than 2%. The regions with a small share of industrial production (Akhangaron, Boka, Bekabad, Kuyichirchik, Akkurgan, Parkent, Piskent) account for almost half (43.3%) of agricultural production. The contribution of the districts to the industrial production of the region has remained practically unchanged over the years [2, 7].

Table 1

Share of regions in industrial production (percent) [3]

Name of cities and districts	2000 y.	2001 y.	2002 y.	2003 y.	2004 y.	2005 y.	2006 y.	2007 y.	2008 y.	2009 y.	2010 y.	2011 y.	2012 y.	2013 y.	2014 y.	2015 y.	2017 y.	2018 y.	2019 y.	Changes
By region:	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	
Cities:																				
Nurafshon	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,9	1,7	1,9	-
Almalik	20,8	21,6	27,3	27,8	29,0	36,0	45,5	36,2	25,2	26,7	27,1	27,6	27,6	24,23	22,9	21,9	27,8	29,4	35,4	14,6
Angren	14,3	13,9	9,9	9,3	7,3	6,09	5,7	5,7	7,6	6,9	6,9	8,0	8,0	8,5	3,7	10,5	7,8	5,9	6	-8,3
Ohangaron	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,0	3,9	2,4	-
Bekabad	8,4	9,2	10,0	11,3	13,9	13,1	11,7	13,8	18,0	15,2	13,9	14,4	14,6	12,3	11,6	9,8	8,4	17,3	11,2	2,8
Chirchik	9,4	9,0	8,9	9,5	12,9	13,6	9,9	10,7	13,2	12,3	11,3	9,9	9,7	8,9	8,4	7,1	8,6	8,5	8,6	-0,8
Yangiyul	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1,7	1,4	1,5	-
Districts:																				
Okkurgan	0,9	1,0	1,0	0,8	1,0	0,9	0,7	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,7	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,6	0,7	0,8	0,6	1,4	0,5
Ohangaron	6,6	6,6	6,4	5,3	4,7	5,6	5,1	6,6	5,9	5,4	4,3	4,2	4,0	6,9	7,5	9,1	0,6	0,4	0,3	-6,3
Bekobod	0,9	1,2	1,1	1,0	0,8	0,7	0,7	0,6	0,8	0,9	0,9	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,7	0,9	0,8	0,5	0,5	-0,4
Bustonlik	4,6	4,5	3,4	3,1	3,3	2,8	2,1	2,5	3,1	3,7	3,8	4,0	3,6	2,2	2,1	1,9	4,0	4,3	4,3	-0,3
Buka	0,6	0,5	0,8	0,9	0,8	0,8	0,6	0,6	0,8	0,8	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,6	0,6	0,8	0,7	0,5	0,4	-0,2
Zangiota	6,0	4,0	5,4	5,0	3,0	3,9	3,6	4,6	5,7	7,3	7,5	7,8	9,0	13,5	14,1	11,8	9,6	8,3	6,2	0,2
Kibray	8,7	7,9	5,9	6,8	6,7	5,7	5,2	5,7	7,6	7,7	8,5	6,2	7,5	5,98	6,2	12,9	8,5	5,8	6,7	-2,0
Kiyichirchik	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,8	0,9	0,9	0,9	0,8	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,7	0,5	0,5	-0,2
Parkent	0,4	0,6	0,6	0,5	0,4	0,3	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,6	0,8	1,1	0,9	1,1	1,0	1,1	0,9	0,7	0,8	0,4
Piskent	0,7	1,0	1,0	0,7	0,6	0,6	0,5	0,6	0,5	0,7	0,6	0,5	0,6	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,9	0,7	0,7	=
Urtachirchik	7,4	8,2	9,0	9,2	7,8	3,1	2,2	4,6	4,3	3,6	5,2	1,9	1,9	1,6	1,7	1,5	1,4	0,8	0,8	-6,6
Chinoz	0,6	1,1	1,6	1,6	1,4	1,0	1,1	0,9	0,1	1,0	1,1	1,2	1,2	1,2	1,1	1,2	1,3	1,0	0,9	+0,3
Yukorichirchik	0,7	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,9	1,1	1,2	1,5	1,5	1,5	2,0	2,7	2,9	2,2	2,0	+1,3
Yangiyul	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0,4	3,2	3,8	-
Tashkent	8,2	8,1	6,1	5,4	4,9	4,5	3,6	4,3	4,4	4,6	4,9	4,1	3,4	4,1	4,6	4,9	2,8	2,4		-5,8

This shows that some districts of the region specialize in industry, while others - in agriculture. This difference in the share of industrial production in the regions is explained by the different distribution of labor resources, natural raw materials, and financial resources by region.

The region has a diversified and metallurgy-oriented industrial sector. The contribution of mechanical engineering, which gives an advantage in the production of high-tech industrial products, is also not good. This suggests that the region's industry specializes in raw materials.

Table 2

Technological structure of industrial production in developed countries, Uzbekistan and Tashkent region [4,160]

Production	Developed countries	Uzbekistan	Tashkent
High-tech production	19	1,6	0,6
Medium-high-tech production	28	29,7	16,1
Medium-low technological production	21	29,8	62,7
Low-tech production	32	38,9	20,6

This contradicts the trends in the development of the world economy, which is characterized by a decrease in the share of the raw materials industry and an increase in the production of mechanical engineering, information technology and high-tech industries. The most important component of the effective development of high-tech industries, as well as production of deep technological processing is the availability of modern production equipment. Depreciation of industrial enterprises in the region remains moderately high. Also, in January-June 2020, the region's industry grew only by 1.8% compared to the same period last year. In a pandemic, the economy needs innovation to become an important component of leading enterprises. The innovative activity of enterprises in the region is very low. This is confirmed by the assessment of the state of innovation activity in the region.

Table 3

Assessment of innovative activity in the region

Indicators	Methodical accuracy	Limit	Regional indicator	Republican index
			2018 y. [5, 40]]	
Wear rate of fixed assets of industrial enterprises of the region, %	Defines the safety level of the manufacturing sector	<40	35,4	38,3
Number of students in secondary specialized and higher educational institutions per 10,000 population	Shows the level of cognitive potential of the region	>600	333	302
Direction of enterprises' own funds for research and development, in% of GRP	Reflects the initial stage of innovation	>2,2	0,14	0,17

Opening activity coefficient, pcs.	Number of applications for patents for inventions per 10,000 population	>500	0,138	0,086
Innovative activity of organizations, %	Contribution of enterprises implementing all types of innovations	>25	1,2	0,92
Technological innovation cost intensity, %	The ratio of the cost of technological innovation to GDP	>2	2,75	0,86
The contribution of innovative products to industry	The main indicator of the effectiveness of innovation	>10	4,93	8,77
Contribution of small businesses adopting technological innovations, %	Demonstrates the innovative activity of small businesses	>10	0,33	0,33
The contribution of research and development costs to the structure of technological innovation	Demonstrates quality investment in technological innovation	>40	10,8	7,4
R&D spending to GDP ratio	Science shows the level of attention given to the development of science	=3	0,14	0,16

The figures in the table above show that the region has a low level of innovation activity. This reduces the possibility of organizing innovative forms of industrial development in the region. During the pandemic, it is important to increase the production of innovative and high-tech products in an environment where special attention is paid to "Development of export potential in regions and industries". The rich natural resources and production potential of the region make it possible to rapidly develop the industrial sector in this area. The recent decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further expand industrial production in the Tashkent region" will allow to build industrial enterprises in the region using modern equipment and technologies during the pandemic [15,6].

IV. RESULTS

Based on the above definition and analysis, if a region mainly consists of industry and agriculture, in the long term, the disbalance (non-competitiveness) of the agricultural sector or insufficient competition in the industrial sector leads to structural instability of manufactured goods or labor activity in the form of labor migration. It is noted that the development of such processes will lead to a further decrease in the quality of human capital in certain regions. In some regions, the concentration of production capacities, their size and positive externalities give these regions an advantage. Ultimately, the development of only certain districts and cities will lead to an increase in the balance between the economic and social status of districts and cities, and the formation of false urbanization in urban areas. Industrial centers such as Chirchik, Angren, Almalyk, which are local points of agglomeration, in practice do not give a synergistic effect to the adjacent territories. The development of only a few agglomerations due to the backwardness of other regions, especially those specializing in agriculture, leads to the emergence of socially strained regions. The region has a developed mining and processing industry. Only in such industrial centers as Chirchik, Angren, Almalyk and Akhangaron, the location of large industrial facilities creates high differentiation.

Agriculture dominates the rural economy. The rich coal deposits of the Tashkent region and the growing demand for chemical and petrochemical products in the world market have allowed the fuel and energy industry to expand the range of goods and exports. However, given the competitiveness of raw materials on the world market and price fluctuations, the lack of diversification of industries can lead to serious situations in the regional economy [12,42]. Therefore, along with the expansion of the raw materials segment in the region, it is necessary to take serious measures for the deep processing of raw materials, thereby creating opportunities for the development of a secondary technological network of industry. Deep processing of cotton fiber, on the one hand, allows the region to develop in light industry, and on the other, to export products with the introduction of new technologies. The production of canned food and dairy products is becoming more widespread in the food industry.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus, the development of innovative products in the region can be characterized by the following trends.

1. Insufficient financing of innovative activities. The limited resource potential of industrial enterprises in the region is one of the major factors in the development of innovative activities. The share of innovation costs in total production is very small. Inefficient funding affects the quality of innovation. This makes it impossible to carry out innovative activities on an ongoing basis. This eliminates the possibility of introducing radical innovations that cover the entire period of the production cycle, from specialization in research to preparation for production technology and the release of new products. For this reason, the number of enterprises engaged in innovative activities is small. In 2018 the total number of organizations producing innovative products was 373. The total number of enterprises in the region is 35 385, of which enterprises producing innovative products make up 1% on average [18,41]. Reasons for low innovation activity:

- lack of financial resources;
- payback period for innovations;
- high risk;
- lack of qualified specialists;
- underdeveloped innovation infrastructure;
- Insufficient innovation potential.

2. Enhancing the role of small business in strengthening innovation processes. As a rule, they can provide greater efficiency in the production and introduction of innovative products with a low assortment in the context of activity, quick adaptation to new changes, deepening diversification and individualization of production. However, it is unlikely that small businesses in the region will have a significant impact on the growth of innovation activity. 89% of enterprises producing innovative products in the area are small businesses. However, 51% of innovative products are produced by large enterprises (11%). Practice shows that even small innovations are carried out only by enterprises that have received financial, intellectual and informational support from the state or large enterprises. Typically, large enterprises conduct their initial analytical processes in small enterprises [19,25].

3. Low efficiency of innovation. The development of high-tech industries and the strengthening of their positions in the world market for high-tech products are impossible without the connection between science and production. Therefore, it is necessary to create a favorable environment for the development of competitive production based on innovative strategic development of basic industries. Therefore, the process of enhancing the innovation processes of the state is of great importance in the implementation of structural transformations in industry based on modernization and diversification, achieving the goals set to increase competitiveness in the country.

In the process of studying the features of the industrial development of the region, it is advisable to carry out the following work in this direction.

The first direction in this area is active government support for investment projects. Of course, this is due to a decrease in the tax on profits of investor enterprises. It is advisable to provide organizational support in complex processes that occur during the implementation of investment projects, especially in a pandemic. Unlike traditional investment projects, the credit risk associated with the development and implementation of innovative projects is much higher. If the private sector considers innovation risks to be excessive, the government should accept these risks and invest in new innovative projects. The main sources of financing are budgetary funds, extra-budgetary funds, own funds of enterprises, loans, innovation and special funds, innovative foreign loans, grants, insurance funds (direct sources), tax incentives and discounts, loan incentives, equipment rental, customs. Currently, one of the most promising forms of innovative financing is venture financing. In this area, it is desirable to develop a system of venture financing with the involvement of commercial banks, insurance companies and others. It is also necessary to attract funds from the private sector and multinational companies in this area, creating additional incentives and preferences to support research [8,15].

The second direction is to ensure the development of the research complex, innovation activities and enterprises, for which all conditions have been created in the region. The region is an active participant in international economic relations. The main task is to involve the enterprises of the region in the process of international cooperation, to facilitate the rapid exchange of best practices. Consumer access to national and neighboring markets is a key factor in the development of a number of priority sectors. Priorities for enhancing innovative factors of long-term growth should be systematic and cover three main areas that have a multiplier effect on the economy as a whole: improving the quality of state institutions and creating the necessary infrastructure for innovative development, improving the quality of human capital, and improving financing of innovative projects. development of the research sector.

The third area is creating conditions for the implementation of innovation policy. The main task here is to attract resources for the implementation of innovative projects, the development of infrastructure to support small businesses. It is also necessary to improve the culture of doing business, increase the investment attractiveness of the region, increase the prestige of innovative business, attract personnel, investments and resources. Consequently, the transition to an innovative model of economic growth will be impossible without profound structural and qualitative changes, including an increase in the share of industry in GRP and the emergence of new types of high-tech products in the industry. Thus, the regional development model should focus on increased investment and technology transfer rather than product diversity. Policy measures in this area include public funding for innovation projects, tax incentives for research projects, support for collaborative technology transfer initiatives, and regulation.

The fourth direction is the creation of conditions for the creation of industrial clusters of innovative production: modernization of existing enterprises and the creation of new enterprises in strategically important areas; Formation of regional orders for industrial enterprises; Support in the implementation of high-tech projects; Inclusion in regional investment programs, Allocation of targeted financing; Development of a marketing strategy for bringing the cluster products to the domestic and foreign markets; Development of the transport infrastructure of the region.

The implementation of measures in these areas will contribute to the optimization of existing production structure, the development of the region's technological potential, and the formation of a high-tech competitive industrial complex in the region. Ultimately, the modernization of the industrial complex will increase the competitiveness of the region's economy and the life quality of the population.

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МЕРЫ ПО СТАБИЛИЗАЦИИ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ РЕГИОНОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПАНДЕМИИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КОМПЛЕКСА ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ)

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Аннотация

В статье описаны особенности промышленного развития Ташкентской области. В рамках одного региона был проанализирован промышленный комплекс, а также приведены взгляды теоретиков на региональное развитие. Проанализированы мнения этих ученых о факторах, влияющих на развитие промышленности в регионе. Экономический потенциал и географическое положение регионов могут привести к четкому разделению отдельных территорий в промышленном производстве. Проведена оценка экономического и промышленного потенциала Ташкентской области. Также анализируется экономический потенциал региона. Рассмотрена роль региональных секторов экономики в стране. Описан экономический потенциал районов и городов, наличие финансовых ресурсов и уровень развития научно-технического прогресса. В нем указывается на необходимость изменения принципов государственного регулирования научной сферы для инновационного развития и эффективного функционирования промышленности региона, зарубежный опыт является примером организационно-экономических мер, поддерживающих инновационное развитие промышленности региона. Также в свою очередь анализируется состав факторов, влияющих на инновационное развитие промышленности региона.

В частности, упор в инновациях делается на развитие человеческого фактора, науки и технологий. Известно, что рост промышленного производства обусловлен не экспансией экстенсивных факторов, а продуманной последовательной политикой в условиях системной рыночной экономики, привлечением иностранных инвестиций, глубокими структурными изменениями в экономике, модернизацией и обновлением производства, новыми экспортно-ориентированными отраслями и предприятиями, организациями через развитие частного предпринимательства. Особое внимание уделяется инновационному развитию промышленного производства. Это вызывает необходимость изучения мирового опыта инновационного развития промышленности региона. В связи с этим в статье используются результаты опыта развитых стран в этой области. Мировой опыт также дает примеры организационных и экономических мер по поддержке инновационного развития промышленности региона. Даны рекомендации по целевому применению этих мер. В выводах представлены рекомендации по устойчивому развитию промышленности региона.

Ключевые слова: регион, промышленность, инновация, технопарк, высокие темпы экономического роста, инновационный кластер.

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